

C-IMMSIM simulation results

May 8, 2025

Abstract

This document includes the plots relative to the simulation and the outcome of the epitope/peptide prediction used.

Produced by the C-IMMSIM Online server available at
<http://c-immsim.iac.rm.cnr.it> (alias to <http://kraken.iac.rm.cnr.it/C-IMMSIM>)

CITATIONS: For publication of results, please cite the following:

Nicolas Rapin, Ole Lund, Massimo Bernaschi, Filippo Castiglione. Computational Immunology Meets Bioinformatics: The Use of Prediction Tools for Molecular Binding in the Simulation of the Immune System. PLoS ONE 5(4): e9862
doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0009862, 2010

A retrospective validation

In-silico evaluation of adenoviral COVID-19 vaccination protocols: Assessment of immunological memory up to 6 months after the third dose. P. Stolfi, F. Castiglione, E. Mastrostefano, I. Di Biase, S. Di Biase, G. Palmieri, A. Prisco. Frontiers in Immunology, 13 (2022) doi: 10.3389/fimmu.2022.998262
<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fimmu.2022.998262>

An in vivo validation

Identification and validation of viral antigens sharing sequence and structural homology with tumor associated antigens (TAAs). C. Ragone, C. Manolio, B. Cavalluzzo, A. Petrizzo, A. Mauriello, M-L. Tornesello, F. M. Buonaguro, F. Castiglione, L. Vitagliano, M. Ruvo, M. Tagliamonte, L. Buonaguro. Journal for ImmunoTherapy of Cancer. 9:e002694 (2021)
<https://jitc.bmj.com/content/9/5/e002694>

Original C-IMMSIM model: www.iac.cnr.it/~filippo/c-immsim

GETTING HELP:

Scientific problems: Filippo Castiglione (filippo dot castiglione at cnr dot it)

Technical problems: Ilaria Gonnella (ilaria dot gonnella at cnr dot it)

Figure 1: Cell counts shown. Legend: Act=active, Intern=internalized the Ag, Pres II = presenting on MHC II, Dup = in the mitotic cycle, Anergic = anergic, Resting = not active.

Figure 2: Legend: symbols as figure above.

Figure 3: The virus, the immunoglobulins and the immunocomplexes.

Figure 4: Concentration of cytokines and interleukins. Inset plot shows danger signal together with leukocyte growth factor IL-2.

Threshold: 9.456400
Max score: 29.236000

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/4946_20250508-195356_5_b6P6KGt8YIls.FSA_1_001

AKQPATLRKYCIEAKLTNTTTDSRCPTQGEPSLNEEQDKRFVCKHSMVDRGWGNGCGLFGKGGIVTCAMFTCKKNMKGKI
VQPENLEYTIVITPHSGEEHAVGNNTGKHGKEVKITPQSSITEAELTGYGTVTMECSPRTGLDFNEMVLLQMEDKAWLVH
RMSYSMCTGKFKVVKEIAETQHGTVIRVQYEGDGSCKIPFEIMDLEKRHLVRLITVNPVIVTEKDRPVNIEAEPFPGD
SYIIIGVEPGQLKLNWFKK

Epitopes of protein 0 -----

0]	pos= 79	score=0.011000	unnormalised=1.2166000000	IVQPENLEY
1]	pos= 120	score=0.041055	unnormalised=4.5406000000	ITEAELTGY
2]	pos= -1	score=0.947945	unnormalised=104.8410000000	non-binding event

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Allele: B0702
Pseudo sequence: KAAREEQSIKAQTRE
Threshold: 8.702800
Max score: 28.406000

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/4946_20250508-195356_5_b6P6KGt8YIls.FSA_1_001

AKQPATLRKYCIEAKLTNTTTDSRCPTQGEPSLNEEQDKRFVCKHSMVDRGWGNGCGLFGKGGIVTCAMFTCKKNMKGKI
VQPENLEYTIVITPHSGEEHAVGNNTGKHGKEVKITPQSSITEAELTGYGTVTMECSPRTGLDFNEMVLLQMEDKAWLVH
RMSYSMCTGKFKVVKEIAETQHGTVIRVQYEGDGSCKIPFEIMDLEKRHLVRLITVNPVIVTEKDRPVNIEAEPFPGD
SYIIIGVEPGQLKLNWFKK

Epitopes of protein 0 -----

0]	pos= 24	score=0.021093	unnormalised=2.2772000000	CPTQGEPSL
1]	pos= 115	score=0.007810	unnormalised=0.8432000000	TPQSSITEA
2]	pos= -1	score=0.971097	unnormalised=104.8410000000	non-binding event

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VQPENLEYTIVITPHSGEEHAVGNNTGKHGKEVKITPQSSITEAELTGYGTVTMECSPRTGLDFNEMVLLQMEDKAWLVH
RMSYSMCTGKFKVVKEIAETQHGTVIRVQYEGDGSCKIPFEIMDLEKRHLVRLITVNPVIVTEKDRPVNIEAEPFPGD
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DoPeptideList_II:
Given the antigen injected creates the list of peptides for all the
NumAgProts proteins and for all i.e., 2 MHCII molecules

Read class II peptide list from file? NO

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Allele: DRB1_0101
Pseudo sequence: KAFAHVEQRKAQTRV
Threshold: 2.392440
Max score: 26.461000

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/4946_20250508-195356_5_b6P6KGt8YIls.FSA_1_001

AKQPATLRKYCIEAKLTNTTDSRCPTQGEPSLNEEQDKRFVCKHSMVDRGWNGCGLFGKGGIVTCAMFTCKKNMKGKI
VQPENLEYTIVITPHSGEEHAVGNNTGKHGKEVKITPQSSITEAELTGYGTVTMECSPRTGLDFNEMVLLQMEDKAWLVH
RMSYSMCTGKFKVVKIEAETQHGTVIRVQYEGDGSCKIPFEIMDLEKRHLVLRITVNPVIVTEKDRPVNIEAEPFPGD
SYIIIGVEPGQLKLNWFKK

Epitopes of protein 0 -----
0] pos= 87 score=0.018094 unnormalised=1.3835600000 YTIVITPHS
1] pos= 131 score=0.037842 unnormalised=2.8935600000 VTMECSPRT
2] pos= 143 score=0.024712 unnormalised=1.8895600000 FNEMVLLQM
3] pos= 157 score=0.050828 unnormalised=3.8865600000 LVHRMSYSM
4] pos= 215 score=0.002662 unnormalised=0.2035600000 LITVNPVIVT
5] pos= 243 score=0.000517 unnormalised=0.0395600000 IIGVEPGQL
6] pos= -1 score=0.865344 unnormalised=66.1680000000 non-binding event

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VQPENLEYTIVITPHSGEEHAVGNNTGKHGKEVKITPQSSITEAELTGYGTVTMECSPRTGLDFNEMVLLQMEDKAWLVH
RMSYSMCTGKFKVVKIEAETQHGTVIRVQYEGDGSCKIPFEIMDLEKRHLVLRITVNPVIVTEKDRPVNIEAEPFPGD
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